

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15348954

Assessing the Challenges of Integrating Eco-Friendly Building Materials in Modern Construction (A Study of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State)

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ABSTRACT

The increasing global population and rising environmental concerns have prompted the urgent need for sustainable practices in the construction industry, particularly the adoption of eco-friendly building materials. In Nigeria, and more specifically Port Harcourt, the persistent use of conventional materials such as cement, asbestos, and synthetic paints continues to degrade the environment and exhaust natural resources. This study investigates the barriers to adopting sustainable eco-friendly building materials and proposes actionable solutions. Using a survey design, data was gathered from architects, builders, quantity surveyors, and structural engineers. Results, analyzed using Relative Severity Index (RSI) and Relative Importance Index (RII), identified government-related barriers—such as lack of policies and incentives—as the most critical. Other challenges include limited awareness, technical expertise, and high perceived costs. Key solutions include public education, media promotion of green practices, and government-backed incentives. The study emphasizes that overcoming these barriers is crucial for reducing environmental impacts and promoting sustainable development in the construction sector.

Keywords: Sustainable construction, Eco-friendly materials, Green building, Barriers, Port Harcourt, Environmental sustainability, Building industry, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The world's population is always growing, and this has raised awareness of the need to preserve the earth's bountiful resources for future housing requirements. The constant growth of the population of Nigeria is resulting in the increase in demand for housing and energy which is one of the major causes of degradation and depletion of the earth's resources. With greater quality, energy efficiency, and the use of recycled and recyclable materials for construction, sustainable construction aims to meet the housing needs of the expanding population and increase building lifespan and occupant health.

Materials are crucial for the construction of buildings. The mechanical strength of the building is a result of the materials' chemical, physical, and mechanical characteristics as well as an appropriate building design. The choice and use of environmentally friendly or sustainable materials should be the first step in the design of sustainable or green buildings. According to Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) for materials to be sustainable it means that they can stand the test of time without having an adverse effect

on the environment, have a minimal negative impact on natural resources, and are safe for people and the environment to use.

Encouraging the construction of sustainable buildings and making sure that they are designed with sustainability in mind is important. There is little public awareness of sustainable building practices, particularly in Rivers State. This may be due to; Lack of institutional structures supporting sustainable or green buildings, insufficient funding to support green construction, limited professional capacity to integrate sustainable buildings into construction, and lack of government support for initiating sustainable construction and the use of sustainable materials for construction purposes.

However, according to Kaanchan and Mahendraa (2017), the level of adoption of sustainable construction techniques is still low due to the complexity of sustainability and the fragmentation of the construction industry. This research is aimed at evaluating the level of awareness of sustainable construction and also promoting sustainable building in Rivers state by integrating sustainable eco – friendly building materials for building construction purposes.

Problem Statement

The increase in the use of conventional building materials (cement, asbestos, paint, vanishes) has led to the deterioration of the environment and depletion of the earth's natural resources (Odeyale & Adegunle, 2008). Although, in Port Harcourt, a few housing developments have been discovered to have some elements of sustainable eco-friendly material (solar installation and water conservation systems) embedded in their design, there is no known evidence of buildings completely built with sustainable eco-friendly materials as Building Professionals (Architects, Structural Engineers, Quantity Surveyors and Builders) along with their clients opt to use the conventional building materials for building projects.

Aim of the study

The aim of the study is to identify and address the barriers to sustainable building material adoption in building projects.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are:

- I. To investigate the barriers of integrating sustainable eco-friendly building materials for building projects in Rivers State.
- II. To proffer solutions to the barriers of integrating sustainable eco-friendly building materials in Rivers State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Materials are essential components of building construction, building materials significantly impact the environment and building users. For a building to be tagged sustainable or green it must be constructed with sustainable or green building materials. Greenhouse gases (GHG) are the main causes of global warming, and buildings are a significant source of GHG emissions (Geng, et al., 2017). However, Nwogu & Emedosi, (2024) asserts the significance of green building projects as a direct panacea of global warming.

According to the EPA, buildings use 41% of the world's energy and produce 40% of the greenhouse gas emissions (Yudelson, 2017). Concerns about the sustainability of buildings have emerged in the building sector. Reducing GHG emissions through sustainable building development would be extremely beneficial. According to the WECD (1987), sustainable development is defined as growth that meets current demands while preserving future generations' ability to meet their own needs. However, according to the INDIA CSR (2023), a green or sustainable building is a structure that minimizes its environmental impact while improving the well-being and comfort of its occupants this is of the same opinion with (WECD, 1987). There is a need to build using sustainable ways since what we build now will shape the built environment of tomorrow and influence future generations' ability to meet their requirements (Dickie and Howard, 2018). Green buildings are built to meet environmental standards and improve operational efficiency, hence reducing the negative influence on the environment (Nwogu & Emedosi, 2024). Green buildings also consider the comfort level of their occupants.

Sustainability refers to having little to no negative impact on people or the environment, whether it be through the use of materials, energy, or practices this is of the same opinion with (Thomas, 2019), he is of the opinion that the concept of sustainable or "green" buildings envisions a novel approach to conserving water, energy, and material resources throughout the building's construction and maintenance, which can lessen or even eliminate the negative environmental effects of structures. Sustainability is a wide, complicated term that has become a major focus in the architecture and construction industries. The concept of sustainability entails improving the quality of life, allowing people to live in a healthy environment with improved social, economic, and environmental conditions (Akadiri et al, 2012). Sustainable construction involves incorporating various environmentally friendly concepts and practices to minimize the impact of building projects on the planet. Some key concepts in sustainable construction include: Energy efficiency, passive design, water efficiency, material efficiency, waste reduction and improved indoor air quality. Heakkinen and Belloni (2011) conducted research to assess the obstacles hindering the adoption of sustainable building materials (SBM) in the construction sector of a developing nation. Utilizing a meticulously designed quantitative questionnaire, data were collected from key stakeholders in the construction industry, the snowball sampling technique and electronic distribution of questionnaires was used. Various statistical analyses such as frequencies, percentiles, relative importance index, Kruskal-Wallis H test, Kendall's coefficient of concordance, and exploratory factor analysis were employed to analyze the gathered data. The research findings demonstrated a correlation between awareness of green building materials, knowledge about sustainable construction, and the actual adoption of sustainable practices. Form the result, implementation of green building is hampered by the fact that the majority of stakeholders are either unaware of or lack information about green or sustainable construction materials.

Characteristics of Sustainable Eco-friendly Building Materials

According to GRIHA, for building material to be termed sustainable it must have these two characteristics;

- Rapidly renewable
- Easily recyclable or reusable.

According to the U.S. Green Building Council (USGBC), rapidly renewable materials are those that can regenerate themselves in 10 years or less. This covers goods derived from plants that are harvested every 10 years or less. According to USGBC, adopting fast renewable content aims to decrease the quantity and caliber of goods made from derivatives of fossil fuels. Among the fast renewable materials used in building construction are hempcrete, tember, bamboo, cork, straw bales, sheep's wool, rammed earth, and reclaimed wood. Used or outdated materials that can be recycled are known as recyclable materials. Reduced garbage in landfills is a requirement for sustainable or green buildings. Recycling materials like metals, glass, paper, and plastic makes this possible (Sheth, 2016). The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) lists the following as the advantages of recycling and reusing building materials:

- Reduces greenhouse gas emissions that contribute to climate change.
- Mitigates pollution by minimizing the necessity for harvesting fresh raw materials.
- Conserves energy.
- Preserves the environment for succeeding generations.
- Decreases the volume of waste requiring recycling or disposal in landfills and incinerators.

Importance of Using Sustainable Eco-friendly Building Materials

Waste reduction, pollution prevention, recyclability, and embodied energy reduction are all factors in the production of sustainable building materials (Usman et al., 2018). He also believes that there are alternatives for waste management, energy efficiency, conservation, nontoxic, longer life, and building operations that result in building materials that are biodegradable, recyclable, and reused. According to Ben-Alon et al. (2019), using sustainable building materials can save material costs, carbon emissions, transportation expenses, and employment prospects. Abimaje et al. (2019) assert that environmentally friendly, cost-effective, versatile, and long-lasting sustainable building materials are necessary. Building materials that are environmentally friendly, like wood, store up to 250 kg/m³ of carbon dioxide (CO₂)

while releasing just 15 kg/m³ into the atmosphere. Steel, concrete, and aluminum, in contrast, do not store carbon dioxide while releasing, respectively, 5320 kg/m³, 120 kg/m³, and 2 2000 kg/m³ into the atmosphere. The embodied energy and carbon of cob are much lower than those of the other traditional materials, according to the environmental effects of cob as an alternative building material from a life cycle perspective. As a result, its use can slow down global warming (Ben-Alon et al., 2019). Additionally, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) listed some advantages of using sustainable building materials, such as preserving resources to lessen negative environmental effects, enhancing environmental quality, and accruing savings through increased productivity and waste reduction.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out to identify and address the barriers to sustainable building material adoption in building projects, the researcher utilized the survey research design, given the nature of the research involving sampling opinions and viewpoints of individuals. The research focused on the Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State, involving key stakeholders in the construction industry, including Architects, Builders, Quantity Surveyors, and Structural Engineers, as respondents. The research instrument used in this study is the questionnaire, participants were given a survey consisting of a set of questions in line with the study objectives. The responses were analyzed using relative severity index (RSI), and relative importance index (RII).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section focuses on analyzing the data collected from fieldwork survey, providing a detailed examination of the primary data using table and bar chart. The primary aim of this analysis is to offer insights that answer the research question, thereby achieving the research objectives.

Table 1: Barriers of integrating sustainable eco-friendly building materials

Barriers of integrating Sustainable Eco-friendly Building materials	RSI
Government Related Barriers	0.95
Knowledge related barriers	0.91
Human related barriers	0.88
Cost & Risk related barriers	0.8
Market related barriers	0.78

Figure: 1: Barriers of integrating Sustainable eco-friendly building materials

Table 1 and Figure 1, shows the barriers of integrating sustainable eco-friendly building materials in Port Harcourt. The relative severity index (RSI) was employed to rank each barriers according to the level of severity. The RSI values obtained ranged from 0.95 – 0.78 with the highest and lowest value going for Government Related Barriers and Market related barriers respectively. This can be attributed to lack of government policy to support sustainable building project. In a similar study, Ebekozien et. al., (2021) found that government related barriers are major cause of the non-adoption of sustainable healthcare building projects. Although government related barriers ranked highest, other barriers (knowledge related barriers, human related barriers, cost and risk related barrier and market related barriers) studied can still play significant role in the choice of sustainable building project in Port Harcourt (Toriola-Coker et. al., 2020).

Table 2: Solutions to Barriers of Integrating Sustainable Eco-friendly Building Materials

Key	Possible solution	RII
Q1	Educating building owners on the future benefits of sustainable building	0.98
Q2	Intensive promotion of sustainable or green building by the government, via: Radio, televisions and social media.	0.97
Q3	Establishment of enticements to inspire invention in sustainable construction by the Government	0.93
Q4	Use of resources from more sustainable source	0.92
Q5	Provision of adequate training centers with adequate funding of research and development to enhance sustainable development	0.89
Q6	Provision of sustainable materials selection criteria	0.79
Q7	Utility of technologies that license the reprocessing of the building components and deconstruction	0.73
Q8	Promotion of sustainable construction by the building industry	0.6
Q9	Employ natural resource management strategy	0.52
Q10	Regular inspection and monitoring of works with set rules and legislation	0.46
Q11	Appraisal of building code and establishment of sustainable building code	0.37

Figure: 2: Solutions to Barriers of Integrating Sustainable Eco-friendly Building Materials

Table 2 and Figure 2, shows the solutions to barriers of integrating sustainable eco-friendly building materials in Port Harcourt. The relative importance index (RII) was employed to rank each solution according to the level of importance. The RII values obtained ranged from 0.98 – 0.37 with the highest and lowest value going for Educating building owners on the future benefits of sustainable building and Appraisal of building code and establishment of sustainable building code. Although the respondents didn't consider that the appraisal of the existing building code and establishment of sustainable building code will yield more results, it can actually set a baseline for the adoption of sustainable building projects (EPA, 2018).

CONCLUSION

Sustainable or green construction also known as eco-friendly construction, focuses on minimizing the environmental impact of building projects. It involves using renewable materials, energy-efficient designs, and reducing waste. This approach helps reduce carbon emissions, conserve natural resources, and create more resilient and energy efficient structures for the future. Based on literature revised, the data collected, the analysis made, the findings obtained and the discussion helps to develop necessary and important conclusion that; Government related barriers which include; lack of government policies and support to encourage sustainable building construction, absence of incentives by the government to encourage sustainable building construction, lack of or ineffective government programs focused on the promotion of green construction and lack of locally or a single unified/standard green building assessment system are major cause of the non-adoption of the use of sustainable eco-friendly building materials for projects in Port Harcourt.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations align with the study's objectives and findings and are outlined as follows:

1. Building owners (the clients) should be properly educated on the future benefits of sustainable/eco-friendly building.
2. The government, should establish enticements to inspire invention in sustainable building construction
3. Intensive promotion of sustainable/green building by the government and the building industry through television, radio and social media.

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